

Saudi Arabia: Leadership, Challenges, Future, and Flautes

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Abstract

This paper discusses the background history of leadership in Saudi Arabia. It will also provide statistics about Saudi Arabia transformation through the years. What are the decisions that are taken by major companies (e.g., Saudi Aramco) to cope with the recession? This paper also discusses some aspects of Saudi vision of 2030: its goals, challenges, and where it might fail.

Keywords: Partnership, Efficiency, Leadership Failures, Stakeholders, Sustainability, Transformational Measures, and Dynamic

1. Historical Background of Saudi Arabia Leadership

Many people when they think of Saudi Arabia they see it as a recent nation that has a short history, but what they do not know that Saudi Arabia first state was established in 1744 under the same basis and leadership of Al-Saud family that ruled Saudi Arabia then and still rules it now. According to the foreign minister of Saudi Arabia Adel al-Jubeir (2016) at Chatham House Meeting, he gave a brief talk on Saudi Arabia's historical background where he mentioned that the royal family that ruled Saudi Arabia lost their kingdom not once, but twice [31]. The first time Al-Saud lost their kingdom was in 1818 by Mohammed bash's ottomans army.

20 years later, Al-Saud returned to rule the kingdom on the same basis. In 1881 the kingdom was demolished under an invasion, in which 20 years later King Abdulaziz Al-Saud was back for the third time to rule Saudi Arabia under the same leadership. That indicates that the royal family had deep connections with the citizens and they were adapted to the Arab culture. Saudi Arabia was united and fixed its borders in 1932. Saudi Arabia is a dynamic country in many aspects. First, the life expectancy was 37 years in the 1930s, now the life expectancy is 74 years, which means that the life expectancy doubled [27, 28, and 29].

Figure 1 Life Expectancy in Saudi Arab

Second, the illiteracy rate was 95% in the 1930s; now there aren't any illiterate people in Saudi Arabia.

Figure 2 Illiteracy Rate

Third, there was no education for women before 1960s, now 55% of college students are women.

Figure 3a Education in the 1930s

Figure 3b Education in the 1930s

Fourth, Saudi Arabia was a country of divided tribes, and now it is united and growing quickly. These are a few of many changes that have been done under the same leadership, which makes it an effective leadership.

2. Saudi Arabia Effective Economic Actions: Vision 2030

Saudi Arabia is a country that depends on oil as the main source of income for the country. In past Saudi Arabia have faced income problems due to the fluctuation of oil price. The Saudi government is trying to solve this problem by diversifying their economy, which means that the country will have many other sources of income, and will not totally be dependent on selling oil, so they created an economic vision to restructure the economy. According to an interview, the Crown Prince Mohammed bin Salman (2016) stated that this vision emphasizes on giving a bigger share of the market and government services to the private sector, and it focuses on taking advantage of its strategic location. In which Saudi Arabia connects three continents: Africa, Asia, and Europe [32]. Saudi Arabia is focusing on creating logistic services (e.g., planes, and trains) because of its important location.

Saudi Arabia location is near to The Bab-el-Mandeb passage which is an essential link in between the Red Ocean and the Indian Ocean and the Suez Canal which leads to The Mediterranean Sea. In the year 2006, approximately 3.3 million barrels or in numbers (520,000m³) quality of oil went through the strait of The Bab-el-Mandeb per day. The quality mentioned was out the total quality of the entire world of around 43 barrels in a day which is (6,800,000 m³/d). According to the Crown Prince Mohammed bin Salman in an interview (2016) that one of the most important logistics that there will be is a causeway that connects Saudi Arabia and Egypt [32]. Also, Saudi Arabia is near to The Strait of Hormuz is a strait between the Arabian Gulf and the Gulf of Oman, where almost 20% of the entire world's petroleum (about 35% of the petroleum imported and exported by sea) goes through the strait, making it an essential location for worldwide trade.

Figure 4 Trade Transits to Saudi Arabia

3. Saudi Arabia Effective Economic Actions: The Largest IPO in History by Far

The main goal of this vision is to establish a sustainable economy. As per an interview in which Mohammed Salman (2016), who is a deputy Crown Prince, stated that selling 5% of Saudi Aramco is a key player in achieving the vision of 2030 [32]. Saudi

Arabia has many natural resources other than oil. The resources are not taken advantage eg., Uranium. According to Saudi Geological Survey, Saudi Arabia has 6% of the world's uranium [36]. Saudi Arabia is determined to do the biggest IPO in history in which they will sell 5% of Saudi Aramco which is estimated to be around 100 billion dollars according to Bloomberg [35]. Why do they want to sell 5% of the greatest oil company in the world? Because since the revenue of the IPO, Saudi Arabia will invest internally, in which they will create more exports than imports to have a positive net port. Saudi Arabia will also invest externally, in which they are looking for potential opportunities to invest in. For example, according to Rakesh Sharma (2016), Saudi Arabia has invested 3.5 billion into uber [38].

4. Saudi Arabia Effective Economic Actions: Increasing Skills of Workforce

Many schools and colleges are trying to create human skills that fit the market. Government plays a big role in creating a work environment that fits the current market needs. Saudi Arabia has shifted its attention from creating highly educated citizens for the market to creating more operation skilled citizens that will be effective and suitable for factories. Saudi Arabia government played a big role in this shift by taking to actions. First, giving salaries for citizens that are studying on how to operate in industries, and strive to acquire the needed skills to become effective in industries [18-22]. The salary is equivalent to 3,000 riyals per month as an incentive. On the other hand, citizens that enter college to graduate with a bachelor degree and become engineers, doctors, or managers are given 990 riyals as an incentive to enter colleges and get a higher education. Second, as per an interview in which Mohammed Salman (2016), who is a deputy Crown Prince that the Saudi government is contracting with companies that specialize in increasing the workforce skills to become more productive and contribute more effectively to the country's economy [32].

5. Challenges

Although the government and the people of Saudi Arabia are very ambitious in achieving the vision of 2030, there are various important aspects that are being neglected [1, 2]. For example, the issue of car accidents in Saudi Arabia remains extremely high. According to Saudi Medical Journal (2015), Saudi Arabia was found to have one of the highest numbers of deaths and is considered to be the country's core

cause of death for 16-30-year-old males [37]. The other challenge is obesity, according to a research done by Memish et al. (2013) out of the 10,735 participants assessed, 28.7% of them were obese, and the obesity frequency was greater among females (24.1% vs. 33.5%) [1, 4, 6, 7, 10].

Figure 4 Obesity in Saudi Arabia

There is a link between obesity and the following; diet, physical activity, marital status, diabetes' diagnoses, hypertension, and hypercholesterolemia, among men. Another link was seen with education and any history of chronic conditions, among women. Earlier researchers in KSA also identified a growing trend related to the obesity's occurrence. The old literature in between the years 1980s to 1990 also shows obesity is close to approximately 20%; the lowest was notices as low as 13% amongst men. It was seen in females as around 26% [5, 6]. The last national survey on obesity in Saudi Arabia which is related [8-10]. In 2005, the factor of risk was studied in association with the (WHO) World Health Organization. From that time, there haven't been surveys that were studied, which made it even close to impossible to raise any doubts against the work of the ministry of Saudi Health is affecting obesity movements. To define present rates of obesity and related to chronic conditions and risk factors. There was a domestic survey in 2013 done in partnership with Institute for Health Metrics [20].

Figure 6. Weight Population Distribution took from National Centre for Chronic Disease Prevention and Health Promotion.

6. Possible Failure

According to Stockholm International Peace Research Institute (SIPRI) 2016. Saudi Arabia is ranked the third highest spending country on military expenditure [33]. Saudi Arabia comes after the United States which is rank first, and China which is ranked second. According to the international institute for strategic studies (2015) Saudi Arabia has spent 81.9 billion dollars on security [11- 13].

Prince of Crown Mohammed bin Salman claimed that the Saudi government is willing to expand military manufacturing by creating an industry that creates military equipment instead of buying military equipment from other countries. But on the other hand, Anthony Cordesman (2016) at a discussion of 2030 vision in The Middle East Institute, Due to the low price of oil, Saudi Arabia can't afford to spend this amount of money on its security [33].

Cordesman also said that the vision 2030 didn't take account the expenses of Saudi Arabia's security. Cordesman emphasized on the point that Saudi Arabia will fail at the aspect of 2030 that involves Saudi Arabia creating a military industrial complex, in which it is planned to supply Saudi Arabia with 50% of military equipment that the government buys 's [33, 34]. "There is no worse investment that a developing country can make than investing in the production of advanced arms" [33]. Due to the nonexistence of technology. The other reason is that it is more expensive to put together other country military parts and to adjust them than simply buying them. Cordesman said that there is a chance in tuning equipment, simple adjustments, giving attention to

the type of military weapons that are cost-effective, and having thorough audits [33].

7. Methodology

The paper has wondered about the leadership skills that college student has, how they will lead their country in the near future, so the researcher has conducted a test which is made by Mindtools team in the college he studied in Jubail University College, which tests how good your leadership skills are? The researcher got 257 responses this test evaluates their leadership skills in five different aspects:

- Self-assurance
- Positive Mental Attitude and Outlook
- Emotional Intelligence (EI)
- Transformational style of Leadership
- Giving a Convincing Vision of the Future

Figure 7 Evaluation of Leadership Skills

The researcher took the answers the most student answered, and evaluated them based on that. The students have answered 18 multiple choice questions. In which they have to choose one of five answers. And each answer is in rank from 1 to 5 points. The answers are: Very often, often, sometimes, rarely, and not at all.

8. Results

The results are not necessarily accurate, but it gives an idea about their leadership skills. Most of the students consider people's skills and interests.

- When assigning tasks, the students rarely doubt themselves and their ability to succeed.
- The students often expect the top-notch result from and do not compromise on them.

- c) The expectations of them from their people to go for hard work is rare and not as much as the researcher does.
- d) They mostly attempt to understand how they feel when they are upset
- e) They sometimes struggle with knowing what to do especially when circumstances change.
- f) Majority of them hardly think the feeling especially the personal ones should not allow hindering their performance and productivity.
- g) As they know the key to success, they are most highly motivated.
- h) They do not like to invest time worrying about the morale of team as they think it's not worth it.
- i) They rarely get upset and worried quite often in the workplace.
- j) It is very often that their actions show people what they want from them.
- k) They often push everyone to achieve the overall objective while working in a team.
- l) They do not compromise on their rules and expectation. They believe that it is easier than to be forced all the time.
- m) They like to plan for the future.
- n) It rarely happens that they feel threatened.
- o) They mostly take time understand the need for people from them.
- p) They are mostly positive about time and ignore the temporary problems they face.
- q) They believe that when individual keep performing a single task again and again until perfected, then the overall teams start to perform well.
- r) They rarely doubt themselves and their ability to succeed.

9. Conclusion

Saudi Arabia is a country that came a long way, has a dynamic culture, and has a long way to go. We still don't know what the future holds for Saudi Arabia. But there is faith in their leadership wisdom, and there is faith in its youth, which will lead their country to what they believe, is suitable for their culture and their religion.

10. References

- [1]. Haslam DW, James WP. Obesity. *Lancet* 2005; 366 (9492):1197–209.
- [2]. Kelsey MM, Zaepfel A, Bjornstad P, Nadeau KJ. Age-related consequences of childhood obesity. *Gerontology* 2014; 60(3):222–8.
- [3]. Withrow D, Alter DA. The economic burden of obesity worldwide: a systematic review of the direct costs of obesity. *Obes Rev* 2011; 12 (2):131–41.
- [4]. Boutayeb A, Boutayeb S. The burden of non-communicable diseases in developing countries. *Int J Equity Health* 2005; 14; 4(1):2.
- [5]. Amuna P, Zotor FB. Epidemiological and nutrition transition in developing countries: impact on human health and development. *Proc Nutr Soc* 2008; 67(1):82–90.
- [6]. Malik VS, Willett WC, Hu FB. Global obesity: trends, risk factors and policy implications. *Nat Rev Endocrinol* 2013; 9 (1):13–27.
- [7]. Nocito A, Balke H. A trip through the history of obesity. *Praxis [Berne]* 1994; 2013; 16; 102 (2):77–83. .
- [8]. Kanter R, Caballero B. Global gender disparities in obesity: a review. *Adv Nutr* 2012; 3(4):491–8.
- [9]. McLaren L. Socioeconomic status and obesity. *Epidemiol Rev* 2007; 29:29–48.
- [10]. Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation. GBD Compare: cause of disease or injury, Saudi Arabia, stacked bar chart. Seattle (WA): University of Washington; 2013.<http://viz.healthmetricsandevaluation.org/gbd-compare/>. Accessed may 5, 2017.
- [11]. Al-Othaimen AI, Al-Nozha M, Osman AK. Obesity: an emerging problem in Saudi Arabia. Analysis of data from the National Nutrition Survey. *East Mediterr Health J* 2007; 13 (2):441–8.
- [12]. Warsy AS, el-Hazmi MA. Diabetes mellitus, hypertension, and obesity — common multifactorial disorders in Saudis. *East Mediterr Health J* 1999; 5(6):1236–42.
- [13]. Al-Nozha MM, Al-Mazrou YY, Al-Maatouq MA, Arafah MR, Khalil MZ, Khan NB, et al. Obesity in Saudi Arabia. *Saudi Med J* 2005;26 (5):824–9.
- [14]. World Health Organization. Global database on body mass index — BMI classification. <http://www.assessmentpsychology.com/icbmi.htm>. Accessed may 5, 2017.
- [15]. Craig CL, Marshall AL, Sjöström M, Bauman AE, Booth ML, Ainsworth BE, et al. International physical activity questionnaire: 12-country reliability and validity. *Med Sci Sports Exerc* 2003; 35(8):1381–95.
- [16]. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey health tech/blood pressure procedures manual; 2009. http://www.cdc.gov/nchs/data/nhanes/nhanes_09_10/BP.pdf. Accessed may 5, 2017.
- [17]. Ministry of Health, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, in collaboration with World Health Organization, EMRO. WHO STEPwise approach to NCD surveillance, country-specific standard report, Saudi Arabia; 2005. http://www.who.int/chp/steps/2005_SaudiArabia_STEPS_Report_EN.pdf. Accessed may 5, 2017.
- [18]. Badran M, Laher I. Obesity in Arabic-speaking countries. *J Obes*; 2011. <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3228340/>. Accessed may 5, 2017.
- [19]. Pan L, Blanck HM, Sherry B, Dalenius K, Grummer-Strawn LM. Trends in the prevalence of extreme obesity among US preschool-aged children living in low-income families, 1998–2010. *JAMA* 2012; 308(24):2563–5.
- [20]. Signs V. Obesity among low-income, preschool-aged children — United States, 2008–2011; 2013. <http://www.cdc.gov/mmwr/preview/mmwrhtml/mm6231a4.htm>. Accessed may 5, 2017.
- [21]. KSA Ministry of Health. National campaign against overweight and obesity 2012. <http://www.moh.gov.sa/en/HealthAwareness/Campaigns/badana/Pages/default.aspx>. Accessed may 5, 2017.
- [22]. Schoenborn CA. Marital status and health: United States, 1999–2002. Advance data from vital and health statistics; no 351. Hyattsville (MD): National Center for Health Statistics; 2004. <http://www.cdc.gov/nchs/data/ad/ad351.pdf>. Accessed may 5, 2017.
- [23]. Drewnowski A. Obesity, diets, and social inequalities. *Nutr Rev* 2009; 67 (Suppl 1):S36–9.
- [24]. Gakidou E. Education, literacy and health outcomes findings. Background paper prepared for the Education for All Global Monitoring Report 2013/4, Teaching and

- learning: achieving quality for all; 2013. <http://unesdoc.unesco.org/images/0022/002259/225929e.pdf> Accessed may 5, 2017.
- [25]. Mackay DF, Gray L, Pell JP. Impact of smoking and smoking cessation on overweight and obesity: Scotland-wide, cross-sectional study on 40,036 participants. *BMC Public Health* 2013; 13:348.
- [26]. Wang Y, Beydoun M. Meat consumption is associated with obesity and central obesity among US adults. *Int J Obes (Lond)* 2009; 33 (6):621–8.
- [27]. Camões M, Oliveira A, Lopes C. The role of physical activity and diet on overall and central obesity incidence. *J Phys Act Health* 2011; 8 (6):811–9.
- [28]. Al-Rukban MO. Obesity among Saudi male adolescents in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. *Saudi Med J* 2003; 24(1):27–33.
- [29]. Lozano R, Naghavi M, Foreman K, Lim S, Shibuya K, Aboyans V, et al. Global and regional mortality from 235 causes of death for 20 age groups in 1990 and 2010: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2010. *Lancet* 2012;380(9859):2095–128. Erratum in: *Lancet* 2013; 23;381(9867):628.
- [30]. Mokdad AH, Jaber S, Aziz MIA, AlBuhairan F, AlGhathithi A, AlHamad NM, et al. The state of health in the Arab world, 1990–2010: an analysis of the burden of diseases, injuries, and risk factors. *Lancet* 2014; 25;383(9914):309–20. .
- [31]. Adel al-Jubeir. talk at Chatham House Meeting 2016. <https://www.chathamhouse.org/event/saudi-arabia-s-regional-foreign-policy-priorities>. Accessed may 5, 2017.
- [32]. Deputy Crown Prince Mohammed bin Salman 2016. <http://english.alarabiya.net/en/media/inside-the-newsroom/2016/04/25/Full-Transcript-of-Prince-Mohammed-bin-Salman-s-Al-Arabiya-interview.html>. Accessed may 5, 2017.
- [33]. Anthony Cordesman (2016) at a discussion of 2030 vision in The Middle East Institute. <http://www.mei.edu/events/saudi-vision-2030-opportunities-and-challenges>. Accessed may 5, 2017.
- [34]. International institute for strategic studies (2015). <http://www.iss.europa.eu/uploads/media/Ale> rt_9_Defence_spending.pdf. Accessed may 5, 2017.
- [35]. John Sfakianakis Bloomberg (2017). <https://www.bloomberg.com/view/articles/2017-04-05/aramco-ipo-is-just-the-first-step-for-saudi-arabia>. Accessed may 5, 2017.
- [36]. Saudi Geological Survey 2015. <http://www.sgs.org.sa/english/pages/default.aspx>. Accessed may 5, 2017.
- [37]. Saudi Medical Journal (2015) <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4404474> Accessed may 5, 2017.
- [38]. Rakesh Sharma (2016) <http://www.investopedia.com/articles/ investing/060516/why-saudi-investment-fund-put-35b-uber.asp>. Accessed may 5, 2017.